

CSIs Final report on activities

2024

Project title: The Museum of Food Waste

Project Acronym: MOFWaste

Leader organization/s: Rio Neiva - Environmental NGO

IMPETUS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101058677. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Instructions

This Final Report is one of the ways in which the IMPETUS consortium will assess the development of your project during the Accelerator programme.

In this document, you will find three sections:

- Project overview: in this section you will provide a brief description of your project
- Project implementation: in this section, you will have to include details of how all the activities initially planned have been developed (from 17-06-2024 to 17-01-2025), if you have achieved the planned KPIs and, if not, to duly justify the deviations from what was planned.
- Main project outputs: in this section, you will be asked to report on the main project outputs you delivered during your project.

Please upload this document on Moodle by 17/01/2024, 23:59 CET in pdf format.

1. Project overview

Project description (approx. 1000 characters)

The Museum of Food Waste aimed to engage students in actively monitoring various forms of food waste across six school canteens in two municipalities in northern Portugal (Esposende and Viana do Castelo), alongside the co-creation of recommendations for interventions to address this issue.

Students (aged 10 to 15 years old) led the process of data collection, analysis and co-creating recommendations.

Teachers and canteen staff were also involved in various phases of the project's implementation, ranging from logistics to data collection, while municipalities and other relevant stakeholders participated in the co-organisation of events and the broader dissemination of the project.

2. Project implementation

2.1. Summary of activities and KPIs

Activity	KPI/s	Planned starting date	Started as scheduled?	Planned end date	Ended as scheduled?	Executed as planned?
A Attend IMPETUS Accelerator training & Aperitives		17th June 2024	Yes	17th January 2025	Yes	Yes
B Participate in IMPETUS impact assessment activities		17th June 2024	Yes	17th January 2025	Yes	Yes
C Participate in IMPETUS communication and dissemination efforts		17th June 2024	Yes	17th January 2025	Yes	Yes

N°1 Stakeholders Engagement	6	June 2024	Yes	June 2024	Yes	Yes
N°2 On-site visits and analysis of school canteens	4	June 2024	Yes	July 2024	Yes	Yes
N°3 Waste Monitoring Infrastructure Installation and Definition of a Monitoring System	5	July 2024	Yes	August 2024	Yes	Yes
N°4 Student-Led Data Collection	9	September 2024	Yes	November 2024	Yes	Yes
N°5 Root Cause Analysis and Co-creation workshops	2	October 2024	Yes	November 2024	Yes	Yes
N°6 Project Dissemination	17	September 2024	Yes	December 2024	Yes	Yes
N°7 Document and Disseminate Results	8	December 2024	Yes	December 2024	Yes	Yes

2.2. *Activities in detail*

Activity 1 - Due 30/06/2024

Description	As in the Work Plan (or latest version) Stakeholder Engagement
Specific tasks	As in the Work Plan (or latest version) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prepare a PowerPoint Presentation summarising project goals, target groups, duration, and other key details to be presented at stakeholders' meetings

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare an email invitation to the school board for an in-person meeting to present project goals, assign teachers, and determine the most suitable grades and subjects for project involvement • Discuss with teachers the best form to elaborate an Informed Consent Form for Project Participation • Share information/engage municipalities about project goals
Key performance indicators	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 Project Presentation - 2 Project Presentations for Board Schools - 2 Project Presentations for Municipalities - 1 Informed Consent Form for Project Participation
Activity 1 implementation (1000 characters max.)	<p>Two tailored PowerPoint presentations were created for different stakeholder groups, such as teachers and local authorities, to introduce the project effectively during meetings, ensuring a shared understanding of its purpose and scope. Meetings with school boards were held (between June and September 2024) to assign teachers and determine the most suitable grades and subjects for student involvement. Teachers also collaborated in designing an informed consent form, ensuring clarity, conciseness, and compliance with data protection guidelines, with a final version developed collectively.</p> <p>To share the project's goals, outcomes, and alignment with municipal priorities, meetings and emails were used. Esposende Municipality expressed interest in expanding the project to three additional schools beyond the original three planned, leading to further discussions with school boards and other stakeholders about the feasibility of these activities</p> <p>Additionally, the NGO ATAHCA, specialising in food waste prevention, was engaged to co-develop a training workshop for canteen staff, a strategic move to build their confidence and engagement throughout the project. Canteen staff play a vital role not only as educational advocates during food delivery, raising awareness about food waste mitigation, but also as key contributors in implementing and adopting strategies to minimise food waste during food preparation.</p>
Deviations activity 1 (1000 characters max.)	<p>The project involved stakeholders at different stages, requiring adjustments to the original timeline in the work plan. For example, while initial meetings with teachers took place in June 2024, follow-up meetings were necessary in September 2024 to validate classes after final student schedules were released.</p>

	<p>Engagement with Esposende Municipality led to the project's expansion. Initially, the work plan included three schools (two in Esposende Municipality and one in Viana do Castelo, involving a total of 60 students). However, due to Esposende Municipality's strong interest, the project was extended to three additional schools. Ultimately, six schools and over 500 students participated.</p> <p>Unfortunately, time and team constraints prevented meetings with the Viana do Castelo Municipality. Instead, we focused on the school in Viana do Castelo, which is near Esposende, while prioritising efforts within Esposende, where our NGO is based.</p> <p>Although training workshops for canteen staff were not initially planned, they proved essential for gaining staff confidence and fostering empathy for the project's goals.</p>
<p>Elements of evidence activity 1</p>	<p>< Project Presentation shared with local authorities https://drive.google.com/file/d/1RFjW5PYjrgMYVZEQUUMTHMCXFFfyIK7q0/view?usp=sharing</p> <p>< Project Presentation shared with School Board, Teachers and Students: https://drive.google.com/file/d/15nNE04_hqUk96whTFwd1qIpvVsxVOIq6/view?usp=sharing</p> <p>< In the Google Sheet "Evidências Disseminação" in Ações Engagement you can access the number of project presentations to different stakeholders (e.g., local authorities, school boards): https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1jox4FZY8ZiIXhOwzaqIIQq4rZc8EMy1F9BgdHRxqR3O/edit?usp=sharing</p> <p>< Informed Consent Form produced and discussed with schools: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1eCiUwzknR-PHY-h0dDRk1ZAAqYZuneb0/view?usp=sharing</p> <p>< Pictures of project presentation and planning activities:</p> <div data-bbox="608 1543 1378 1877"></div>

	<p>More pictures can be accessed in the following link: https://photos.app.goo.gl/CH1H8uYaPcMeCSik8</p> <p>< Pictures of workshops co-organised with ATAHCA NGO</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> </div> <p>More pictures can be accessed in the following links:</p> <p>Workshop 1: https://photos.app.goo.gl/bKbUqc4FxpoczNCxk7</p> <p>Workshop 2: https://photos.app.goo.gl/3ATFja1X8vaCsC449</p>
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Activity 2 - Due 31/07/2024

Description	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <p>On-site visits and analysis of school canteens</p>
Specific tasks	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the current knowledge of canteen staff regarding food waste valorisation and disposal processes, identifying difficulties and opportunities • Analyse the types and locations of waste containers

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determine the best locations and schedules for monitoring to minimise disruptions to the normal functioning of canteens • Identify optimal places to display food waste monitoring data in order to capture students' attention and engagement • Selection and buying scales and waste bins
Key performance indicators	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 on-site visits - Google Sheet “Project Planning” (including a list of materials needed for project execution, associated costs and suppliers; Organisation of project invoices)
Activity 2 implementation (1000 characters max.)	<p>To evaluate canteen staff's knowledge of food waste prevention, valorisation (e.g., converting food waste in composting) and disposal, informal interviews and observations were conducted to assess understanding, identify gaps, and gather insights for integrating prevention practices. This feedback shaped targeted training sessions (please see Activity 4 for further details). Waste containers were also mapped to evaluate capacities and placements, ensuring the prevention of material accumulation and avoiding potential confusion in food waste disposal throughout the project.</p> <p>To minimise disruptions to the processes of food provision, we collaborated with staff to determine optimal locations and schedules for waste monitoring, aligning them with peak waste generation times for accurate data collection. Potential display areas for food waste awareness, such as canteen entrances and common areas, were identified to maximise visibility and student engagement, sparking curiosity and participation in reduction efforts.</p> <p>Scales and waste bins were selected based on the needs identified during evaluations, ensuring suitability for the project's goals.</p>
Deviations activity 2 (1000 characters max.)	<p>The visits to school canteens took place later than initially planned (originally set for 31-07-2024). We needed to adjust for staff holidays during the summer period. Additionally, more visits were required than originally planned in the work plan, as more schools were involved in the project.</p>
Elements of evidence activity 2	<p>< In the Google Sheet “Planeamento-global-mofwaste_impetus-2024”, “Cantinas-caracterização” you can see some data collected during school visits for canteen characterisation:</p> <p>https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1waOU5RoltDrwTniNypIf0UNSMvgbtSLmRzbM86NXeqA/edit?usp=sharing</p> <p>< Pictures taken during school visits (canteens characterisation):</p>

Activity 3 - Due 31/08/2024

Description	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <p>Waste Monitoring Infrastructure Installation and Definition of a Monitoring System</p>
Specific tasks	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Install waste bins specifically designated for food waste, spoiled food, food surplus, and plate leftovers ● Implement a simple and intuitive labeling system for students and canteen staff ● Creation of a Monitoring Data Sheet ● Development of a Google Sheet to compile and analyse data from each school (teachers will have permission to visualize the document)
Key performance indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 On-site visits to install waste infrastructures and implement the labeling system - 1 Monitoring Data Sheet - 1 Google Sheet “Project Data & Analysis”
Activity 3 implementation (1000 characters max.)	<p>Waste bins for non-edible food waste, food surplus, and plate leftovers were installed in strategic locations within each canteen to ensure effective waste separation. A labelling system with clear, easily recognisable food waste categories was developed to make separation intuitive for both students and canteen staff.</p> <p>A monitoring toolkit, comprising a protocol and a standardised monitoring data sheet, was created to ensure consistency in data collection across all schools. The protocol provided detailed instructions for conducting data collection independently, while the monitoring sheet included fields for the date, waste type/category, quantity (in kilograms), and additional comments. Training sessions were conducted for staff, students, and teachers on accurate data recording (refer to activity 4 for further details).</p> <p>A centralised Google Sheet was developed to compile and analyse the data. Organised with separate tabs for each school, the sheet featured automatic calculations and tools for trend analysis, enabling efficient and effective data management.</p>
Deviations activity 3 (1000 characters max.)	<p>This activity was initially scheduled to conclude in August 2024 but was extended into September 2024 to ensure that all content produced (e.g., the monitoring toolkit) was accessible to all citizen-scientists. Additionally, the extension allowed for the proper installation of materials in the canteens.</p> <p>Please note that in the Work Plan, we initially planned to monitor four types of food waste: spoiled food, non-consumable food waste, food surplus, and plate</p>

leftovers. However, during the canteen characterisation phase and discussions with canteen staff, we realised that the likelihood of finding spoiled food was very low, as they adhere to strict guidelines from local authorities to ensure compliance with hygiene and food safety standards. Therefore, throughout the project, we monitored the following three categories: non-edible food waste, food surplus, and plate leftovers.

< Toolkit produced for data collection (protocol + monitoring sheet):
https://drive.google.com/file/d/1_dmeXJCoIAQGxEFqyBVE8uCdWLIjD7SD_/view

#MoFazaste MÚLTIPO DO DESPERDÍCIO ALIMENTAR

Protocolo Monitorização Desperdício Alimentar

Encontra no KIT de Monitorização!

Fichas Monitorização
Etiquetas Desperdício
Câmara
Calculadora
Batas Laboratório
Sacos biodegradáveis

1º Passo - Preparado para ser cientista?

- Decide em grupo quem fica responsável por tirar fotos, fotografar, ler o protocolo e pesquisar.
- Visita a **base de laboratório** para evitar que te saiam.
- Retira a **Ficha de Monitorização** e a **câmara do KIT**.
- Faz um **registo fotográfico** do processo e do desperdício realizado e entrega as tuas fotos através do **QR Code**.

2º Passo - Vamos monitorizar!

Apresenta o **menu** do dia e preenche os ingredientes da refeição.

Apresenta o **menu** do dia e preenche os ingredientes da refeição.

Apresenta o **menu** do dia e preenche os ingredientes da refeição.

Apresenta o **menu** do dia e preenche os ingredientes da refeição.

3º Passo - Não deixes nada para trás!

- Se necessário, coloca sacos novos biodegradáveis em cada categoria.
- Coloca material no KIT Monitorização.
- Assigura-te que o espaço fica devidamente higienizado.

4º Passo - Comunica os resultados!

- Partilha os resultados com a tua família, amigos? Vamos acabar como desperdiçador?

Refeição (descrição principais ingredientes)

Sopa	Cenoura, Batata
Prato	Massa Bolonhesa (carne vaca)
Sobremesa / Fruta	Maçã, Banana, Laranja

Refeições (nº)

Previstas	180
Servidas	173

Categorias de Desperdício (kg)

		Líquidos (inclui sopa)	Sólidos	Total (L + S)
1	Cozinha - Sobras	0,700	3,200	3,900
	Cozinha - Não Comestível	---	0,340	0,340
	Refeitório - Não Consumido	0,660	10,500	11,160

Observações Massa foi o ingrediente mais desperdiçado pelos alunos

Responsáveis Monitorização Ana, Paulo, André, Rita

Ano / Turma 7º B - Apúlia

Página 1

Elements of evidence activity 3

For each school, we included a distinct QR code in the protocols. This QR code was created for students to upload pictures of the monitoring process. Additionally, we included in the toolkit an example of a completed monitoring sheet, which could be consulted in case of any doubts.

< Data Introduction - Google Sheet shared with students and teacher for data uploading:
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1NB3187BMzbWq18NrcwYolvkTzyPqZKcS_9WPi71qfrQ/edit?usp=sharing

< Labelling system for identification of different categories of food waste:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGcFmr-dww/5J2ExgeoDkY5sUTi2I7Ggw/edit?utm_content=DAGcFmr-dww&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton

	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 30%;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Desperdício Produção</p> <div style="border: 1px solid white; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> <p style="font-size: 2em; color: white;">1</p> <p style="color: white;">Cozinha Sobras</p> <p style="font-size: 0.8em; color: white;">(arroz, batatas, sopa, massa, salada...)</p> </div> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: 0.8em; color: white;">#Mofwaste</p> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 30%;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Desperdício Produção</p> <div style="border: 1px solid white; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> <p style="font-size: 2em; color: white;">2</p> <p style="color: white;">Cozinha Não Comestível</p> <p style="font-size: 0.8em; color: white;">(cascas, ossos, espinhas...)</p> </div> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: 0.8em; color: white;">#Mofwaste</p> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 30%;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Desperdício Consumo</p> <div style="border: 1px solid white; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> <p style="font-size: 2em; color: white;">3</p> <p style="color: white;">Refeitório Não consumido</p> <p style="font-size: 0.8em; color: white;">(desperdício da refeição: líquidos + sólidos)</p> <p style="font-size: 0.7em; color: white;">• não incluir resíduos de papel e plástico.</p> </div> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: 0.8em; color: white;">#Mofwaste</p> </div> </div> <p style="margin-top: 20px;">< Data Analysis - Google Sheet https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/16niVv1BD52tjU2S2gAwlGqeGZ0WyoQ7zkWSSz24erlg/edit?usp=sharing</p>
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Activity 4 - Due 30/11/2024

<p>Description</p>	<p style="color: red;">As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <p>Student-led data collection</p>
<p>Specific tasks</p>	<p style="color: red;">As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Present the project to students; ● Recruit student volunteers to regularly monitor and record the different categories of food waste; ● Train students/teachers/school staff in monitoring food waste; ● Supervise data collection over 1 week to secure data quality; ● Analyse the data collected in relevant school subjects (e.g., maths, biology)
<p>Key performance indicators</p>	<p style="color: red;">As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 On-site visits to present the project and engage students - 3 On-site visits to build the capacity of students/teachers/school staff in monitoring food waste - 3 On-site visits to supervise data collection over 1 week to secure data quality

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “To be defined” Supervise data collection and exploration by regularly contacting teachers
<p>Activity 4 implementation (1000 characters max.)</p>	<p>We conducted capacity-building workshops for students, teachers, and canteen staff involved in data collection. These sessions included demonstrations of the data collection process using a monitoring toolkit, which featured labelled food waste categories, a protocol with clear instructions, and supporting materials. These hands-on activities ensured participants felt confident in the process.</p> <p>During data collection, an average of four students, accompanied by a teacher, recorded data on food waste categories at the end of lunch and during class time. Integrating data collection into class hours was crucial for maintaining consistency over 40 days. Five different classes were assigned to different days of the week, reducing disruption to regular lessons and preventing lack of interest among students over the data collection period.</p> <p>The project was also introduced to students not directly involved in data collection. Presentations were delivered to demonstrate how food waste could be explored in subjects like arts, Portuguese language, and mathematics, among others. Collected data was also integrated into lessons in subjects such as mathematics and biology. The project was incorporated into at least nine different subjects.</p> <p>At one school (EB Forjães, in the Municipality of Esposende), a one-week contest on Zero Food Waste was held during the monitoring activity. This initiative has been conducted at the school since the first edition of MOFWaste in 2021. During the contest, certain classes take on a vigilant role, ensuring that their peers do not waste their meals. At the end of the year, the groups with the least food waste are rewarded (in this case, with a canoeing session provided by us on the river). This competition was instrumental in assessing the potential reduction in food waste over the 40-day period and evaluating the effectiveness of such contests in promoting behavioural changes.</p>
<p>Deviations activity 4 (1000 characters max.)</p>	<p>As mentioned in Activity 1, the project was expanded to include a total of 536 students, far exceeding the initially planned 60 students. This expansion required a significant increase in the number of sessions to present the project and provide training for students, teachers, and canteen staff. However, this did not compromise the quality of the project or its overall impact. Expanding the study to include a larger number of schools also enables comparative analysis and the generation of more robust data, which can be effectively shared with municipalities</p>
<p>Elements of evidence activity 4</p>	

	<p>< Google Sheets with information on dates for capacitation training and data collection per school:</p> <p>EBACO EB Apúlia EB Marinhas EB Forjães EB Foz do Neia ESHM</p> <p>< Google Sheets “Evidências Disseminação” in Ações Engagement with the number of presentation actions:</p> <p>https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1jox4FZY8ZiIXhOwzaqllQq4rZc8EMyIF9BgdHRxqR3O/edit?gid=0#gid=0</p> <p>< Image of the Contest Zero Waste held in EB Forjães (14 to 18 october 2024): https://photos.app.goo.gl/QzS5iYo44BpLLpaP8</p>
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Activity 5 - Due 30/11/2024

<p>Description</p>	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <p>Root Cause Analysis and Co-creation workshops</p>
<p>Specific tasks</p>	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a questionnaire to identify the root causes of each type of food waste • Collaborate with students, teachers and canteen staff to gain diverse perspectives • Facilitate brainstorming sessions to co-create recommendations for interventions targeting each category of food waste
<p>Key performance indicators</p>	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <p>1 - Questionnaire “Root causes of food waste disposal” 2 - Co-creation/Recommendation Workshops</p>

<p>Activity 5 implementation (1000 characters max.)</p>	<p>A questionnaire was created to identify the root causes of food waste, focusing on factors like meal quality, awareness of food waste, and portion sizes. It included both closed questions for quantitative data and open-ended questions for qualitative insights, and was open to the entire school community (i.e., students participating and non-participating in data collection, teachers, board directors, operational staff).</p> <p>Brainstorming sessions were organised with students to discuss current practices and generate potential solutions. These sessions were facilitated by teachers during class time, ensuring minimal disruption to the project's other activities. These sessions resulted in recommendations that included practical strategies to address identified challenges, such as adjusting portion sizes, revising menu options, improving storage practices, and raising awareness through campaigns. These recommendations will be shared with local authorities in the final report (see activity 7 for further details).</p> <p>During the capacity-building workshops for data collection, we also encouraged discussions with canteen staff and teachers on challenges and best practices.</p>
<p>Deviations activity 5 (1000 characters max.)</p>	<p>No deviations.</p>
<p>Elements of evidence activity 5</p>	<p>< Google Forms Questionnaire https://forms.gle/M8dPKjam1WRxYRnP6</p> <p>< Poster Questionnaire https://drive.google.com/file/d/1lcFVw9FLsrJv6K3dha8_nmhazzdeFUrP/view?usp=sharing</p>

< Example of recommendations produced by students:

Images also available in the following links:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/19Lnm4WPU1Aq_x_xUp7szTHpG0pNQRvFi/view?usp=sharing

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1OlcZ3okR_8eNeu8Pdydb5ChIEzcgMhEx/view?usp=sharing

More recommendations can be accessed in the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1d_zhK4gnw0xpFP7MuT7ZQ1Z7vJpIWjFc?usp=sharing

Activity 6 - Due 31/12/2024

Description	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <p>Project Dissemination</p>
Specific tasks	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate project aims in social media channels, Rio Neiva Newsletter and School Journal • Update MOFWaste Website
Key performance indicators	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 Posts/Stories in Social Media (Facebook and Instagram) • 4 Brief paragraphs presenting project goals and main results in Rio Neiva Newsletter • 2 Article for the Journal School • 1 Selection of images taken during the project stored in a Google Drive folder "MOFWaste Communication"
Activity 6 implementation (1000 characters max.)	<p>Regular dissemination was carried out throughout the project's development to keep the school community and broader audiences updated on the project's results via posts on social media (Facebook and Instagram). We also managed to communicate key activities and achievements regularly through our membership newsletter (about 700 subscribers). Schools involved in the project also produced posts on their social media about their actions. And the website was recently updated with additional information on the methodologies applied (citizen science), images, project activities, results, and funding from IMPETUS – EU.</p>
Deviations activity 6 (1000 characters max.)	<p>We achieved more KPIs than initially planned. Specifically, during the project, we exceeded most of the KPIs as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 14 posts/stories on social media (Facebook and Instagram); • 5 brief paragraphs presenting the project's goals and main results in the Rio Neiva Newsletter; • 6 files containing images of project activities per school.
Elements of evidence activity 6	

Example of a post disseminating activities in Facebook. The post was also replicated on Instagram.

MOFWaste - O Museu do Desperdício Alimentar

Iniciamos reuniões de discussão com as escolas participantes no projeto, o Agrupamento de Escolas António Rodrigues Sampaio, e a EB Castelo do Neiva, em Viana do Castelo, de modo a definir estratégia de implementação do **MOFWaste** no próximo ano letivo. Paralelamente, a estas sessões a nossa equipa tem recebido mentoria em Ciência Cidadã, de forma a integrar esta metodologia no projeto. O MOFWaste é financiado pelo programa "**IMPETUS**" da União Europeia.

Example of a concise paragraph highlighting activities featured in the Rio Neiva newsletter (Rio Neiva Newsletter, June 2024 Edition, <https://us20.campaign-archive.com/?u=d77569143ff15bab18fa55400&id=a613fedcb5>)

< In the Google Sheet "Evidências Disseminação" please see Disseminação Online for additional evidences: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1jox4FZY8ZjiXhOwzaqllOq4rZc8EMy1F9BgdHRxqR3O/edit?usp=sharing>

	<p>MOFWaste - EB ACO 8 de out. - 22 de nov. de 2024</p> <p>Reproduzir destaques</p> <p>Francisca Costa, Francisca Costa, Francisca Costa, Matilde Ferreira, Matilde Ferreira</p> <p>Google Pictures file example shared with school for pictures uploading.</p>
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Activity 7 - Due 31/12/2024

Description	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <p>Document and Disseminate Results</p>
Specific tasks	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Systematise and analyse data ● Publish data on food waste and resulting recommendations ● Design/print of MUIs of results ● Document and disseminate success stories and challenges faced during the project
Key performance indicators	<p>As in the Work Plan (or latest version)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 Results Report - 6 MUIs - dissemination on site - 1 Final Event

<p>Activity 7 implementation (1000 characters max.)</p>	<p>The data collected throughout the project was organised and analysed in a centralised Google Sheet. Excel tools were used to calculate averages, trends, and variations, with visualisations such as graphs and charts to aid interpretation. Qualitative data, including feedback from questionnaires and brainstorming sessions, was reviewed to identify recurring themes and root causes of food waste, highlighting both areas of success and those requiring further attention.</p> <p>The findings and recommendations were compiled into a comprehensive presentation report, summarising key insights. This report will be shared on the project's website and discussed with schools and local authorities.</p> <p>MUPIs displaying the results were designed, printed, and will be exhibited for two weeks at each school. During the exhibition, students involved in data collection will guide tours, explaining the main findings and the methodology to their peers.</p> <p>Additionally, a questionnaire was distributed to canteen staff to assess the project's impact on their work and gather suggestions for improvements.</p>
<p>Deviations activity 7 (1000 characters max.)</p>	<p>We initially planned to produce a total of six MUPIs for the exhibition. However, given the significance of the results and the importance of presenting them in a more attractive way, we decided to produce a total of eight MUPIs.</p> <p>We also intended to organise a final event at the end of the project. However, this proved impossible to carry out in December, given the volume of results we needed to compile. Additionally, we realised it would be challenging to select a single school for the final event, considering that six schools were involved in the project. Therefore, we decided to focus our efforts on the travelling exhibition and tasked the students responsible for data collection from each school with sharing the results with their entire school community (please see below the link to the document "Exposição_MOFWaste_Impetus2024" (already shared with School boards) with starting dates for the itinerancy and other details.</p>
<p>Elements of evidence activity 7</p>	<p>< Data analysis - Google Sheet</p> <p>https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/16niVv1BD52tjU2S2gAwIGqeGZ0WyoQ7zkWSSz24erlg/edit?usp=sharing</p> <p>< 8 MUPIS produced for an itinerant exhibition:</p> <p>https://rioneiva.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/rioneiva_mupis.pdf</p>

#MOFWaste

MUSEU DO DESPERDÍCIO ALIMENTAR

PORQUÊ?!

Porque o desperdício alimentar devia pertencer ao passado!

O Projeto #MOFWaste tem como objetivo monitorizar o desperdício alimentar nas cantinas escolares dos Municípios de Esposende e Viana do Castelo, através de uma abordagem de ciência cidadã, e envolver os estudantes e restante comunidade educativa, na co-criação de recomendações para a sua prevenção.

RIGNEIVA.COM/MOFWASTE

Confrontar & Mobilizar

Identificar causas, discutir e criar estratégias.

de 20 ações de sensibilização e discussão

Criar Pontes

Aproximar a comunidade educativa da ciência.

Agitar Consciências

Pesar diferentes categorias do desperdício.

Analisar dados e revelar a dimensão do problema.

6 ESCOLAS
40 DIAS DE MONITORIZAÇÃO
6,24 TONELADAS DE BIORRESÍDUOS

#MOFWaste

MUSEU DO DESPERDÍCIO ALIMENTAR

Agitar Consciências

Distribuição por categoria Biorresíduos (%) Média 6 Escolas

Comida	25%
Comida não consumida	22%
Resíduos	53%

Média de Biorresíduos por refeição servida (g) por Escolas

Escola 1	126
Escola 2	54
Escola 3	27
Escola 4	126
Escola 5	135
Escola 6	102
Média	102,5

E SE FOSSE NUM ANO?

Estimativa Total Biorresíduos: 6 Escolas: **37** Toneladas

Raízes — Submergir no problema

Conhecer comportamentos e práticas.

Questionário 177 respostas

53,4% Cota de refeição.
55% Recolha que há desperdício na escola e preocupa-se com o tema.
89,3% Acha que há mais desperdício alimentar no refeitório.

Desafios: Serão quais intervenções, normas ou regras implementadas para a redução do desperdício, quer individual e quer coletivo?
Boas Práticas: Existem práticas que no comportamento dos alunos, uso de pratos e copos, aproveitamento de sobras e outros, poderiam ser implementadas em todas as escolas? Indicar qual delas se considera mais adequada para a sua escola.

Recolha de práticas

Co-criação: Soluções

Participar ativamente na resolução através da partilha de recomendações.

- Ementas + criativas**
Liberdade para criar e valorizar integralmente alimentos.
- Dose Certa**
Ajustar quantidades da refeição.
- Leva-me contigo**
Vender sobras a preços acessíveis em formato "take away".
- Solidariedade**
Reencaminhar sobras de boa qualidade para populações vulneráveis.
- Gamificação**
Comunicação + desafiante para > consciência.
- Desperdício a circular**
Criar valor e encaminhar para compostagem ou animais domésticos.

Impacto & Legado

O desperdício vai ficar no passado, mas o MOFWaste **não!**

6 ESCOLAS > de 500 estudantes
> de 50 professores
Integração Interdisciplinar em > de 9 disciplinas

2 MUNICÍPIOS Alargamento do projeto a + 3 escolas.

KIT de Monitorização Desperdício Alimentar
Ferramenta de aproximação da comunidade educativa ao processo científico, passível de replicação a outras escolas, promovendo a escalabilidade e sustentabilidade do projeto.

Aprofundamento de Novas Metodologias

Participação da Equipa Rio Neiva em:
Bootcamp | IMPETUS | Ciência Cidadã

< Exposição_MOFWaste_IMPETUS2024.pdf

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1aYDHVxpF4CucJb9PA93OIyhokoYX15as/vie w?usp=sharing>

	<p>< Final report (PowerPoint format) to be shared with local authorities and School board:</p> <p>https://drive.google.com/file/d/1-vmPGxe_4lf1w8didQmzf4eVasprz3fB/view?usp=sharing</p> <p>< Questionnaire Staff - canteens</p> <p>https://forms.gle/uDC84BcUG7JX7xgK6</p>
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3 Main project outputs

Please, indicate the total number of project outputs produced since the beginning of your participation in IMPETUS.

- Itinerant Exhibition (8 MUPIS/Posters)
- Toolkit for Food Waste Monitoring
- Final Report
- Dissemination Article
- Project video

These outputs can also be accessed in an updated version of MOFWaste website: www.rioneiva.com/mofwaste

1. VOLUNTEERS/CITIZEN SCIENTISTS engaged in the project

Total number			
586			
Gender distribution		*Age distribution	
<i>Men</i>	293	<i>0-14</i>	536
<i>Women</i>	293	<i>15-24</i>	
<i>Non-binary persons</i>		<i>25-49</i>	
<i>Prefer not to say</i>		<i>50-64</i>	50
<i>Self-described</i>		<i>65-79</i>	
<i>Eventual missing data</i>		<i>80 and more</i>	
***Total	586	***Total	586

2. Did you work with any of these UNDER-REPRESENTED or VULNERABLE GROUPS¹?

Ethnic minorities

Migrants **X**

People with functional diversity **X**

Isolated elderly people

LGTBIQ+ people

Minors **X**

Low-income households

Others:

No

3. If YES, please elaborate.

In both municipalities (Esposende and Viana do Castelo), schools have a mix of nationalities. Migrants from Brazil, Venezuela, Colombia, Ukraine, Pakistan, among other countries, are inclusively integrated into regular classes, with an additional Portuguese language subject to aid their learning and adaptation. Given that they are well integrated into the classes, they were also part of the project. The same applies to individuals with functional diversity. The Portuguese Ministry of Education advises schools to integrate students with functional diversity into regular classes whenever possible. Therefore, we also had students with varying degrees of autism, for instance, participating in data collection and in-class analysis.

4. Activities in which the volunteers/citizen scientists were engaged in your project.²:

- *Problem framing (define research design, map and connect stakeholders, ethical considerations)*
- *Defining a research question*
- *Task design*
- *Developing data gathering instruments*
- *Collecting data* **x**
- *Processing and curating data* **x**
- *Analysing data* **x**
- *Interpreting data* **x**

¹ *Definition EIGE: Groups of persons that experience a higher risk of poverty, social exclusion, discrimination and violence than the general population*

² *Based on the participatory research design available here: <https://actionproject.eu/toolkit/>*

- *Sharing and communicating results x*
- *Evaluating and assessing impact*
- *Policy-impact related activities (drafting policy recommendations, organising advocacy meetings, etc.)*
- *Co-designing activities x*

5. Describe the TYPE OF DATA COLLECTED by the volunteers/citizen scientists (if applicable) (for example: pictures, water samples, mobility tracking, etc.)

The volunteers/citizen scientists involved in the project monitored and recorded three different categories of food waste (inedible food waste, food surplus, and plate leftovers) in school canteens over a period of 40 days. Throughout the process, each school was assigned a specific file on Google Drive and Photos, where data and images taken by the students during the monitoring process could be uploaded.

The images can be accessed in following Google Photos links:

- [MOFWaste EBACO](#)
- [MOFWaste EB Apúlia](#)
- [MOFWaste EB Marinhas](#)
- [MOFWaste EB Forjães](#)
- [MOFWaste EB Foz do Neiva](#)
- [MOFWaste ESHM](#)

We also share the GD links where data per/school was introduced:

- Data Sheet [EBACO](#)
- Data Sheet [EB Apúlia](#)
- Data Sheet [EB Marinhas](#)
- Data Sheet [EB Forjães](#)
- Data Sheet [EB Foz do Neiva](#)
- Data Sheet [ESHM](#)

As mentioned before, each school was also responsible for discussing and sharing recommendations to prevent food waste (please see activity 5, above).

6. Number of BILATERAL MEETINGS held with KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Type of meeting	Number of meetings	Total number of participants	Very short description about the subject of the meeting and the type of stakeholders
Face to face	1	3	Type of stakeholder: Municipality of Esposende. The meeting aimed to present the project and assess the potential for scaling it up to more schools in the municipality.
Online	3	12	Type of stakeholders: Municipality of Esposende and ATAHCA NGO. The meetings with the Municipality of Esposende were held to provide updates on project progress and to validate the contents produced, particularly the project exhibition. Meetings with ATAHCA were focused on co-organising two capacity-building workshops for school canteen staff, centred on ideas and suggestions for leftover recipes. These workshops, led by ATAHCA, took place in September (18th and 20th).

7. Number of face to face and online EVENTS organised (excluding bilateral meetings with key stakeholders).

Type of event	Number of events	Total number of participants	Very short description about the event
Face to face	3	100	<p>We organised an event for a local charity aimed at presenting the project's objectives, along with a hands-on Zero Food Waste activity featuring recipe examples to help avoid food waste. Participants in the workshops were mainly children aged 2 to 5 years old, as well as educators and staff from the charity canteen, totalling 66 participants. This event coincided with Food Week, a theme celebrated in schools and charities during October (the month of food). A selection of pictures taken during this event can be accessed here.</p> <p>Additionally, we co-organised a training session for all staff working in school canteens and charities in the Municipality of Esposende, in collaboration with a nutritionist from the ATAHCA NGO. This event, titled "Nada se Perde, Tudo se Cozinha" (<i>Nothing is Lost, Everything is Cooked</i>), included staff already participating in the project, as well as others. The main aim of the event was to promote ideas and suggestions for recipes using leftovers. A total of 34 people participated in the workshop. A selection of photographs can be accessed here.</p>

Online	2	1604	We took the opportunity to promote MOFWaste's activities on social media (Facebook and Instagram) on relevant days and weeks as part of our online awareness strategy. For instance, during the European Week for Waste Reduction (EWWR) 2024, which focused on the theme of food waste, and on World Food Day, we communicated the project's objectives and the actions being implemented in schools.

8. DATASETS produced, DATA POINTS for each of them (if possible) and which datasets are available as Open Data.

Name of the dataset	Number of data points (also approximately)	Is it already available as Open Data?	Link to the repository/website (if already available as open data)	Intention to publish it as Open Data in the future
MOFWaste análise dados		No		Yes
		Yes/No		Yes/No

9. During your project, have you written or contributed to any SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS based on your project? (Peer-reviewed articles, non-peer-reviewed articles, books, book chapters, or presentations at conferences)

No contributions were made.

N	Information on the publication	Type of publication	Status	Is it Open access?	Ratio between male and female authors
1	-	-	-	-	-

10. Did you develop any OTHER SCIENTIFIC OUTPUTS? (Training materials, scientific reports, theses, collections of samples, online repositories, research tools or methodologies, etc.)

N	Very short description about the nature of the output and its scope	Type of output	Is it Open Access?	Link to the repository/website
1	We developed a protocol and a data collection sheet specifically designed to be accessible and suitable for students aged 10 to 15 years.	Training Materials (Protocol and data sheet collection)	Yes	https://www.rioneiva.com/mofwaste These materials can be directly accessed here

11. Did you develop any other NON-SCIENTIFIC OUTPUTS (reports/articles in online/printed newspapers, articles/contents on external websites, interviews, policy briefs, other policy-related documents, etc.)

N	Very short description about the nature of the output and its scope	Type of output	Is it Open Access?	Link to the repository/website
1	Presentation of a report summarising the project results for discussion, aimed at local authorities and school boards.	Report Presentation	No	
2	Exhibition: Eight posters showcasing the project results, which will be displayed on a rotating basis in schools.	Project Exhibition	Yes	rioneiva.com/mofwaste

12. If applicable, number of communication outputs (youtube videos, blog posts, press releases, social media posts, podcasts, etc.) .

Type of communication outputs	Total number of contents published
Social media posts (Facebook and Instagram)	14
Membership Newsletter	5
Podcast	1
Blog posts (eg., Rodriguinho - School Jornal)	1

13. Number of people reached via social media and communication channels (Facebook, X, Instagram, Youtube, podcast, project or organisation website, etc)

Social media or other communication channels	Number of people reached (followers, likes, or analytics, please specify)
Facebook, Instagram	5095
Membership Newsletter	3500
Podcast	No information. It was made by a participant school and we are not able to see numbers.
Blog post	School Community, approx. 1444 students.

14. Number of EMPLOYEES RECRUITED THANKS to the project, differentiating between full-time and part-time workers (researchers, administrative staff, social media staff, legal staff, etc.).

Total N. of employees recruited thanks to the project	N. of full-time workers	N. of part-time workers
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<p>None, although the support of IMPETUS was essential in contributing to the overall funding of our staff members.</p>		
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15. Do you think your project generated a cost or time saving for your stakeholders?

The theme of food waste is a strategic priority for both municipalities participating in the project, as well as for their commitment to achieving the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). While they already carry out related projects in schools, they face limitations in terms of time and human resources to ensure the sustainability of these activities in the long term. They also lack training in citizen science approaches. Therefore, our project was essential, aligning with their strategies and helping to save both time and costs.

16. NUMBER OF HOURS dedicated to the project by VOLUNTEERS

We considered only students and estimated an average of one hour per student for data collection and training. Accordingly, we estimate a total of 536 hours for 536 students.

17. NUMBER OF HOURS of YOUR TEAM dedicated to citizens' engagement, training and support.

We do not have precise information on this. We estimate 3,840 hours (please refer to column "E" in the Google Sheet titled "[Evidências Disseminação](#)", where we calculate an estimate of the number of hours per session). However, this does not account for all the preparation time required for each activity.

18. How many PROPOSALS or REQUESTS FOR FUNDS were submitted as a result of the project?

Number of proposals	Describe the type of funding you tried to access
0	None, yet.

19. Please indicate the amount of additional public/private funding (in Euros) awarded to you, in addition to IMPETUS (indicate 0 if you didn't attract any additional funding).

0.
